

Steering Decisions : Unveiling Consumer Perceptions and Preferences in Indian Automotive Market with a Spotlight on Tamil Nadu

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Abstract : *This study employs a quantitative approach to examine car ownership trends and consumer preferences among different socioeconomic classes in Tiruchirappalli, Madurai, and Dindigul, Tamil Nadu. The increase in car ownership is linked to the easy availability of auto loans, rising salaries, and higher purchasing power of the middle-income class. India's expanding middle class, rising cost of living, and rapid urbanization contribute to its prominence as a major vehicle market. Analyzing these factors can help businesses refine their products, marketing strategies, and distribution methods to effectively target this growing market. The study involved 300 respondents, evenly distributed across the three cities, using a simple random sampling technique and collecting data via a structured questionnaire, both online and in print. Data analysis was conducted using Microsoft Excel and SPSS 26, including reliability testing via Cronbach's alpha, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), and Pearson's chi-square tests. Ethical considerations, such as informed consent and data confidentiality, were adhered to. Despite existing research on factors influencing car ownership, a gap remains in understanding how these factors vary across socioeconomic classes. Addressing this gap could offer valuable insights into car ownership trends in India and inform policymakers on sustainability and regulatory impacts.*

Keywords : Car Ownership, Socioeconomic Status, Auto Loans, Middle-income Class, Tamil Nadu, Consumer Preferences.

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Introduction

Understanding consumer behavior involves studying how people make choices among various products and how they see themselves about those choices. Analyzing consumer attitudes is essential for understanding their motivations and decision-making processes. A customer's reaction to a product or service is influenced by their beliefs, attitudes, and past experiences. Marketers use this mix of information to create persuasive messages that can shape consumer behavior.

As of 2021, India ranked as the fourth-largest automobile market in the world. By 2022, the country's automotive sector had grown significantly, becoming the fourth-largest globally in terms of value. India surpassed Japan and Germany to become the third-largest vehicle market worldwide based on sales figures in 2022.

India's auto industry now generates over \$100 billion in revenue, accounts for 8% of the nation's exports, and contributes 2.3% to the GDP. Prominent Indian automakers include Maruti Suzuki, Ashok Leyland, Tata Motors, Mahindra, Tractors and Farm Equipment Limited, Royal Enfield, Eicher Motors, Hindustan Motors, Kerala Automobiles Limited, Tara International, Vehicle Factory Jabalpur, and Reva.

The automotive sector has a significant environmental impact due to carbon emissions, air pollution, and resource consumption. Examining this sector is crucial for identifying sustainable practices, such as promoting electric transportation, improving fuel efficiency, adopting cleaner manufacturing methods, and addressing environmental concerns. The electric vehicle (EV) industry is expected to reach annual sales of 10 million by 2030, growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 49% from 2022 to 2030. By 2030, the EV sector is anticipated to create 50 million direct and indirect jobs. The Indian automobile industry is projected to be worth over \$222 billion by 2030, contribute 8% to the country's total exports, account for 7.1% of the GDP, and rank third globally.

Review of Literature

(Claudia & Enrico Ivaldi , Paolo Parra Saiani, 2019) Says there are two goals for the paper. The first goal of the paper is to advance our understanding of the factors that influence people's decision to use car sharing by putting forth a novel viewpoint based on how people feel about driving their cars. Second, by

analyzing the socio-demographic influences on car-sharing behavior, the research adds to our knowledge of the link between the pace of acceptance of car-sharing services and attitudes about using a private automobile.

(Gebhardt, 2021) based on his research, claims that in many nations around the world, automobiles remain the most popular form of transportation. However, reducing motorized transportation is essential to achieving sustainability. Therefore, it's essential to understand and consider the viewpoint of car users when creating alternative mobility ideas. (Ashath, 2014) believes that India's automobile industry is rapidly expanding. As their per capita income rises people are increasingly inclined to purchase luxury items like cars, diamonds, etc.

(Pawar, 2022) concludes his research by stating that the type and brand image of automobiles and their manufacturers have an impact on consumer purchasing decisions. thus they must preserve their brand identities. (Gheorghe & Dan, 2011) Price is one of the four traditional components of the marketing mix, and for durable goods like automobiles, price is a key factor in the decision to purchase.

(Doshi & Parmar, 2016) One of the sectors in our economy that are growing the fastest is the auto industry. It has now become a staple of our daily lives, which is why car manufacturers focus more on the common man market. The choice to purchase a car is not a personal one. (Sangeeta Gupta, 2013) Today's world is characterized by the consumer, and as a result, manufacturers and marketers not only consider how to satisfy customers but also go beyond what is necessary to delight them.

(Priya et al., 2019) The important factors taken into account when purchasing flavorful, delectable foods were product quality, brand recognition, product variety, and limited promotional strategy. Various studies show that the number of family members and the monthly family income has a significant impact on the number of tasty bites of sweets and savory foods consumed.

(Dr. R.Krishna Kumari1 & C.Saranya2, 2019) According to the research, most people prefer macro cars, which include Tata and Mahindra. Preference for Indian brand cars is influenced by the quality, after-sales service, and brand name.(Bhardwaj, 2019) The top automakers must create vehicles that guarantee comfort, safety, and a sense of freedom, even while taking into account environmental concerns and consumer perceptions of alternative modes of transportation.

(Akdođan, 2021) In addition to being a key component of the marketing mix, a product's price has a significant impact on consumer preferences. Price can have an impact on a product's perceived value, quality, and consumer's ability to choose between different alternatives.

(Maharana & Acharya, 2023) Said in this study that the goal of this research is to investigate customer preferences. Through examination of the elements impacting purchasing choices, an effort has been made to gauge the loyalty of customers concerning these goods. Through random selection, information was gathered from 550 chosen respondents in the Odisha district of Sambalpur. According to the objective, the data have been analyzed using exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, structural equation modeling, the Garrett Ranking Technique, and ANOVA.

(Shetty & Khaladkar, 2023) said in this research that the frequency, mean, and one-way ANOVA were used as methods of analysis. The statistical research design was used here and the questionnaires were sent to respondents digitally. The questions were structured as statements that asked the responder to rate their impressions and give them a Likert scale score. There are two parts to the questionnaires. The demographic data is presented first, then the main body of the study or several assertions. Convenience sampling is used as a sample method. 219 investors make up the study's sample population.

(Abdul & Soundararajan, 2022) said in this study that the conceptual research project aims to develop a model that shows the connection between consumers' intent to make purchases via the Internet and the different levels of perceived risk. The model, which is based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), highlights the role of perceived behavioral control to modify the strength of the perceived risk and purchase intent and its connection. To investigate the connection between consumers' actual buying behavior and their purchase intentions, this model employs hierarchical regression. The findings help to clarify the complex relationships between various risk indicators and the desire to do an online transaction. The sense of interactive control as a relationship mediator, which has enormous consequences in both theory and practice, is what predominantly influences online purchases.

(Chawla & Singh, 2022) Said in this study that the automobile industry's success rests on offering exceptional after-sales services in addition to selling customers outstanding cars. To better comprehend how the beneficial after-sales services provided by the car sector may boost client satisfaction. For this study, non-

probabilistic snowball sampling, a quantitative analytical technique, was used to gather data from 336 automobile company customers. Both exploratory factor analysis and Cronbach's internal consistency have been used to look into the links between the variables.

(Roy, 2022) The study includes a variety of consumer behavior research studies that relate to both offline and online buying. It offers a thorough introduction to consumer behavior in addition to a range of other behaviorally associated topics. Variables were produced via an in-depth analysis of several research articles that affect the purchase options of consumers. The purpose of the research is to identify the factors that affect consumers' decision-making when they purchase both online and offline. The research observed several factors that affect consumers' purchasing decisions for both online and offline shopping.

(Cicila, 2021) This research focuses on how customers perceive the availability of grievance redressal procedures in the banking industry. The ANOVA test and multiple regression have both been used as statistical procedures to determine the outcomes. Through an interview schedule, data from 384 bank clients were gathered. The study's findings showed that customers are less aware of banks' external processes than of their internal ones when it comes to dispute resolution procedures and mechanisms.

(Kumar & Gulati, 2017) To better understand how consumers in rural Haryana, India, perceive organic goods a study has been undertaken. The goal of the research is to understand how consumers genuinely interact with organic goods. 110 respondents were selected as a sample for the study's purposes. (Chon, 1989) If the performance meets or surpasses the consumer's expectations, the consumer will have a positive disconfirmation, which might result in more purchases. On the other side, if the performance falls short of expectations, customers will experience negative disconfirmation. The customer will not be happy and will look for alternate possibilities.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the Tamil Nadu automobile industry.
2. To evaluate the consumer's decision-making process for purchases.
3. To classify the buying behavior of Indian consumers.
4. To determine consumer satisfaction with automobiles and their buying patterns.

Research Methodology

Research Design and Sampling : This study uses a quantitative approach to explore the factors influencing car ownership and consumer preferences among different socioeconomic classes in Tiruchirappalli, Madurai, and Dindigul, Tamil Nadu. As per statistician's recommendation a sample size of 273 was calculated using a sample size calculator based on a 90% confidence level and a $\pm 5\%$ margin of error, assuming a 50% population proportion. To enhance the robustness of our findings, we collected data from 300 respondents, equally split across the three cities. A simple random sampling technique was employed to ensure the sample accurately represents the population. For the digital distribution, we utilized random sampling tools to select respondents from platforms like Instagram, Facebook, Telegram, WhatsApp, and email. Physical surveys were conducted in public areas, and we took steps to prevent duplicate responses.

Data Collection : Data were collected through a structured questionnaire, available both online and in print, catering to those with limited digital access. The questionnaire featured a five-point Likert scale to gauge consumer decision-making regarding car purchases. Before full distribution, a pilot test helped refine the questions for clarity.

Data Analysis : We entered the collected data into Microsoft Excel and analyzed it using SPSS 26. To ensure the reliability of our questionnaire, we checked for Cronbach's alpha, achieving a satisfactory value above 0.7. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used to uncover underlying factors, with the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure confirming the adequacy of our data for this analysis. We also used Pearson's chi-square test to explore the relationships between socioeconomic status and car ownership preferences.

Ethical Considerations and Limitations : We prioritized ethical considerations by obtaining informed consent from all participants and ensuring their data remained confidential and secure, with anonymization of responses. While we made every effort to reach a diverse group of participants, we recognize potential biases due to self-reporting and the limited generalizability of our findings to other urban and rural areas in Tamil Nadu.

Additional Considerations : We collected demographic details such as age, gender, income, and education level to provide deeper context and control variables in our analysis. We took care to design the questionnaire neutrally and trained physical data collectors to minimize potential biases.

Figure-1 : Neural Scheme of Consumer Buying Behavior (The Conceptual Model)

Source: Authors' own Compilation

Purchasing Decision Process

Selecting a product to purchase involves several steps for the consumer. Marketers need to understand how consumers make their final purchasing decisions. Four stages will be experienced by the consumer, according to Philip Kotler. A lot of social and psychological involvement is implied in the behavior of buying a car, making it a fairly complex one. As a consequence, the customer will progress through each step of the purchasing decision-making process, as depicted in Figure-2.

Figure-2 : The Purchase Decision Making Process (Philip Kotler)

Source: Authors' own Compilation

Discussions

Table-1 : Demographic Profile

NAME OF THE VARIABLE.	DEMOGRAPHIC	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS	MALE	159	53.0
	FEMALE	141	47.0
THE AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS (IN YEARS)	20-30	96	27.3
	30-40	82	32.0
	40-50	76	25.3
	ABOVE 50	46	15.3
OCCUPATION OF THE RESPONDENTS	EMPLOYEE OF GOVERNMENT SECTOR	43	14.3
	EMPLOYEE OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR	124	41.3
	RESPONDENTS WHO ARE SELF-EMPLOYED	103	34.3
	RESPONDENTS WHO ARE RETIRED	30	10.0
MONTHLY INCOME	UPTO 30000 Rupees	38	12.7
	30000-40000 Rupees	70	23.3
	40000-50000 Rupees	93	31.0
	ABOVE 50000 Rupees	99	33.0
AREA OF RESIDENCE	RURAL AREA	153	49.0
	URBAN AREA	147	51.0
CAR BRANDS (PREFERRED BY RESPONDENTS)	MARUTHI SUZUKI	36	12.0
	HYUNDAI	93	31.0
	MAHINDRA	22	7.3
	TATA	37	12.3
	OTHERS	112	37.3
CAR SEGMENTS (PREFERRED BY RESPONDENTS)	HATCHBACK	40	13.3
	SEDAN CAR	93	30.7
	SUV	92	31.0
	MUV	75	25.0
FUEL TYPES OF CARS (PREFERED BY RESPONDENTS)	Petrol	117	39.0
	LPG/CNG	53	17.7
	Diesel	91	30.3
	Electricity	39	13.0

Source: Authors' own Compilation

From the above table, it shows that. The majority (53%) of the total respondents were male and the remaining (47%) were female respondents. And (32%) of the Respondents belong to the 30 – 40 age categories. (41.3%) of the respondents were Government employees. (33%) of respondents are earning above 50,000 rupees of income per month. Most of the respondents (51%) are living in urban areas and (37.3%) of them prefer other foreign brands of cars. (31%) of respondents preferred SUV segment cars and Most of the (39%) of respondents preferred petrol engines.

Data trust is built on a solid foundation of data reliability, which is the accuracy and completeness of the data. As a measurement of internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha indicates how closely a set of things are linked to one another. It is widely accepted that this number has to be higher than 0.7. Cronbach's Alpha values of 0.90 or above indicate remarkable internal consistency, 0.80 or higher is good, 0.70 or higher is acceptable, 0.60 or higher is probable, 0.50 or more is poor, and 0.50 or below is unacceptable.

Table-2 : Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha's Result	Number of Items.,
.755	15

Source: Authors' own Compilation

From the reliability analysis test, it was found that to be acceptable at .755, the rule of alphas result must be ($>$ or $=$) to .7, and the alpha's result is greater than .7 (alpha $>$.7).

Table-3 : KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO measures Adequacy.,		.832
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity.	Approx. Chi-Square.	3272.944
	Degree of freedom	105
	Sigft,	< 0.001

Source: Authors' own Compilation

EFA is often used to assess a measure's internal reliability and determine its factor structure. Before evaluating the factors, it is customary to run the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) adequacy test and Bartlett's test of sphericity, commonalities, and variances. A value greater than 6 is considered acceptable. However, for the propinquity of variables, which is also supported by Snedecor and Cochran,

Bartlett's test statistics must be significant. The variances are homogenous because the p-value is less than 0.5. The usual acceptance standard for factor loading is more than 0.5. The greater an item's affinity with a certain component, the higher the loading factor.

The KMO index defines sampling adequacy. The KMO test has a valid and acceptable value of (.832), which is more than (0.5), and can be utilized to carry out the data reduction procedure. Bartlett's test of Sphericity assists in determining if more data analysis is warranted in light of the factor analysis results. The level of significance (< 0.001), it may be stated that there is a substantial degree of correlation between the variables, making factor analysis appropriate.

The extent to which something corresponds with all other things is known as the communality. Greater communalities are preferable. It may be difficult for a given variable to load considerably on any factor if its communalities are low.

Table-4 : The Communalities

S.No.	NAME OF THE VARIABLES.	INITIAL	EXTRACTION
1	Technological Advancements	1.000	.571
2	Fuel Economy	1.000	.812
3	Ground Clearance	1.000	.712
4	Resale Value	1.000	.674
5	Pricing	1.000	.671
6	Comfort in Driving	1.000	.865
7	Driving Style	1.000	.900
8	Symbol of Status in Society	1.000	.894
9	Availability of Loans	1.000	.806
10	Religious and Ethical Considerations	1.000	.865
11	Gender Roles and Expectations	1.000	.811
12	Advertising and Media Influence	1.000	.716
13	Family Requirement	1.000	.709
14	Dealership Experience	1.000	.652
15	Sales After Service	1.000	.347

Source: Authors' own Compilation

Initially, every variable in the communality is anticipated to share 100% variance. As a result, each item starts with a value of 1.00, indicating that each item shares 100% of the variation. The extraction values range from 0.347 to 0.900, suggesting that the extracted item has a minimum variance share of 34.7% and a maximum variance share of 90%.

Table-5 : Total Explained Variance

S.no.	The Eigen values			Extraction Squared Loadings			Rotated Squared Loadings		
	The values of Eigen	Variance percentage	The total percentage	The values of Eigen	Variance percentage	The total percentage	Total	Variance percentage	The total percentage
1	4.980	33.202	33.202	4.980	33.202	33.202	3.431	22.872	22.872
2	2.418	16.122	49.324	2.418	16.122	49.324	2.804	18.695	41.567
3	1.971	13.142	62.466	1.971	13.142	62.466	2.669	17.794	59.361
4	1.636	10.907	73.373	1.636	10.907	73.373	2.102	14.012	73.373
5	.740	4.934	78.307						
6	.569	3.791	82.098						
7	.507	3.379	85.476						
8	.446	2.976	88.453						
9	.379	2.529	90.982						
10	.352	2.345	93.327						
11	.273	1.820	95.147						
12	.238	1.587	96.734						
13	.200	1.335	98.069						
14	.168	1.120	99.189						
15	.122	.811	100.000						

Principal Component technique is used for the extraction

Source: Authors' own Compilation

The first component's total variance contribution is (33.202), followed by the second component's (16.122), the third component's (13.142), and the fourth component (10.907). The Eigen value of a particular factor assesses the variance in all variables that the factor accounts for. It is also obvious that out of the given set of variables, there are a total of four components with Eigen values greater than 1 they are 1, 2, 3, and 4 and their Eigen values are (4.980), (2.418), (1.971), and (1.636) respectively.

Figure-3 : Scree Plot

Source: Authors' own Compilation

The components are displayed on the X-axis of the Scree plot along with the corresponding Eigenvalues on the Y-axis. These Eigenvalues are regarded as the first four components: (4.980), (2.418), (1.971), and (1.636). Since the highest Eigenvalue is 4.980, this factor is the most significant, followed by all others. These four components are important in this research since they all have Eigenvalues larger than 1 and share the largest variation.

Table-6 : Rotated Component Matrix

Factors	Variables	Component				Variance percentage	The values of Eigen
		1	2	3	4		
Personal Factors	Technological Advancements	.877				33.202	4.980
	Fuel Economy	.827					
	Ground Clearance	.792					
	Resale Value	.766					
	Pricing	.739					
Social Factors	Comfort in Driving		.911			16.122	2.418
	Driving Style		.892				
	Symbol of Status in Society		.886				
	Availability of Loans		.505				

(Contd...)

Cultural Factors	Religious and Ethical Considerations			.935		13.142	1.971
	Gender Roles and Expectations			.928			
	Advertising and Media Influence			.925			
Psychological Factors	Family Requirement			.832		10.907	1.636
	Dealership Experience			.813			
	Sales After Service			.785			
The principal Component technique is used for the extraction and the Varimax technique is used for the Rotation.							

Source : Authors' own Compilation.

The Eigen value of factor 1 is 4.980 with 33.202% of variance, for factor 2 is 2.418 with 16.122% of variance, factor 3 is 1.971 with 13.142% of variance and factor 4 is 1.636 with 10.907% of variance. The variables are related to Personal Factors which has very high significant loading on the variable Technological Advancements(0.877) and the least factor loading on price which is (0.739), same as the variables are related to social Factors which has a very high significant loading on the variable Comfort in Driving which is (0.911) and the least factor loaded on the availability of car loans which is (0.505), and for the third-factor variables which are related to cultural factors which have very high significant loading on the Religious and Ethical Considerations(0.935) and the least factor loading on Advertising and Media Influence which is (0.925), and finally The variables are related to Psychological Factors which has very high significant loading on the variable Family Requirements (0.832) and moderate factor loading on Dealership Experience which is (0.813) and the least factor loading on sales after service which is (0.785)

Table-7 : Analysis of Purchasing Decision of Car

Overall purchasing decision towards the car		
Level of satisfaction	Frequency	Valid Percent
SATISFIED	111	37.0
NEUTRAL	81	27.0
DISSATISFIED	108	36.0
Total	300	100.0

Source: Authors' own Compilation

From the above Table no: 7, it shows that the majority of the respondents 111 were satisfied with their purchasing decision towards the car which is (37%)

and 108 respondents were dissatisfied which is (36%) and 81 respondents were neutral in their purchasing decision towards the car which is (27%) of the respondents.

Research Hypothesis

- **HO1** : The Purchasing decision of the car was not dependent on the gender of the respondents
- **HO2** : The Purchasing decision of the car was not dependent on the age of the respondents
- **HO3** : The Purchasing decision of a car was not dependent on the occupation of the respondents
- **HO4** : The Purchasing decision of a car was not dependent on monthly income of the respondents

Table-8 : Cross-tabulation of Gender and Overall Satisfaction for Purchasing Decision of Car

	The Value.	Degree of freedom	Asytc Sig
Pearson,s Chi-Square value	22.197 ^a	4	.000
Number of Valid Cases.	300		

Source: Authors' own Compilation

The above-mentioned Table no. 7 shows that the decision to purchase a car was influenced by gender; the value of P is lower than 0.001. As a result, the null hypothesis was declined.

Table-9 : Cross-tabulation of Age and Overall Satisfaction for Purchasing Decision of Car

	The Value.	Degree of freedom	Asytc Sig
Pearson,s Chi-Square value	59.487 ^a	12	.000
Number of Valid Cases.	300		

Source: Authors' own Compilation

In the preceding table, the alternative hypothesis was accepted at (< 0.001), showing that there is a substantial relation between age and overall satisfaction with a vehicle purchase decision.

Table-10 : Cross-tabulation of Occupation and Overall Satisfaction for Purchasing Decision of Car

	The Value.	Degree of freedom	Asytc Sig
Pearson,s Chi-Square value	110.575 ^a	12	.000
Number of Valid Cases.	300		

Source: Authors' own Compilation

The table reveals that the P value is (< 0.001) thus it disproves the Null Hypothesis, indicating that there is a direct association between occupation and overall satisfaction with car purchasing decisions.

Table-11 : Cross-tabulation of Monthly Income and Overall Satisfaction for Purchasing Decision of Car

	The Value.	Degree of freedom	Asytc Sig
Pearson,s Chi-Square value	73.857 ^a	12	.000
Number of Valid Cases.	300		

Source: Authors' own Compilation

The alternative hypothesis is valid since the P value is (< 0.001), demonstrating a clear relation between monthly income and overall satisfaction with the choice to purchase a car.

Limitations

The research does have some limitations. This study's limitations are brought on by several uncontrollable variables. The location of the research is the first limitation of the proposed study. Data collection for this study is concentrated on the cities of the Tamilnadu state, namely Tiruchirappalli, Madurai, and Dindigul. According to the convenience of the researcher. Future studies might include every state in India, with a focus on testing the quality component to see whether the findings are consistent with those of the current research.

Conclusion

India is one of the world's major vehicle markets due to its expanding middle class, rising cost of living, and rapidly increasing urbanization. Businesses can modify their goods, marketing plans, and distribution methods to successfully get into this huge market by analyzing the sector to acquire insights into customer behavior, preferences, and buying patterns. The vehicle industry in India is governed by several rules and regulations including emissions, safety requirements, fuel economy, taxes, and trade agreements. Policymakers and regulators may better protect the interests of consumers by promoting sustainability, innovation, and the expansion of the sector by evaluating the effects of current rules and developing new ones. Existing studies highlight many factors influencing car ownership and preferences in India, like car sharing attitudes, income growth, brand image, price sensitivity, and after-sales services. But there's a missing piece: how do these factors change across different socioeconomic classes? We don't fully understand how economic growth, marketing strategies, sustainability concerns, and online versus offline buying habits impact the upper, middle, and lower classes differently. Filling this gap could give us a clearer picture of car ownership trends in India.

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